

DOUBLE SLIT EXPERIMENT- EYE TEST MACHINE

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ABSTRACT

Double slit experiment new eye test machine made using that method, using only the method without using it directly. Using the double slit experiment method, eye tests can be performed in different ways based on the situation and context. AI can also be added to this in different ways based on the situation and context. Using AI.

KEYWORDS

Double slit eye test machine

INTRODUCTION

We know the special feature of the double slit experiment .when electrons pass through ,if we do not observe them ,they travel in the form of wave, and if we observe them, they travel in the form of particle. The double slit experiment not used directly Only that method is used here instead, only its idea or method is used.

If an eye examination is performed using the double slit experiment method, if we can't see it at all object and objects or picture and pictures, there will be an imaginary wave pattern on the screen. If we can see it clearly, the object, objects on the screen will be at the same level. If we can see a little, those in the form of a wave come at a medium same level, while those in the form of an imaginary wave come at a medium different level, according to the eye vision. Because. This method can be converted to different methods without changing the ideas depending on the design and structure of the device and software, the double slit experiment is not used directly, only ideas, methods, and imagination are used here. The double slit experiment can be imaginatively added to devices and software. The objects observed during eye examinations can be imaginatively given the characteristics of particles tested in the double slit experiment, because here AI and other technologies are used based on the situation and context.

This method allows for a very accurate and clear eye test. Using the double slit experiment method. Vision can be accurately tested in different ways without directly using the double slit experiment. We know about the uniqueness of the eye. We know about eye examination. Examination helps prevent eye diseases. This date is about a method that can eye examination very accurately and without any mistakes. The theory states that eye examinations can be different methods, without using the double slit experiment directly, using this method. The theory is that without making changes to the double slit experiment method, it is possible to perform eye examinations in different ways by making modifications to technologies and software. It is also said that by adding this method to software and technologies, it is possible to

perform eye examinations in different ways. we know that the uniqueness of the experiment is that by adding this method to eye testing, levels of vision both in the visible and invisible. Help of AI. Using AI.

No device, software or mathematical calculation is mentioned here, because many different devices and software can be made using this method, and this method can be added to them. And mathematics can be used in different ways. using AI.

AI can be added in different ways and developed in different ways based on the situation and context we are measuring. The reason is that the double slit experiment is not used directly, but rather it is used in various ways.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The theory was written based on studies and observations conducted during the double slit experiment.

METHODOLOGY

Double slit experiment is not used directly, but rather its method is used.

DOUBLE SLIT EYE TEST MACHINE

We know the special feature of the double slit experiment. when electrons pass through, if we do not observe them, they travel in the form of wave, and if we observe them, they travel in the form of particle. Using this method, not used directly. Only that method is used, [the double slit experiment not used directly. Only that method is used here. Instead, only its idea or method is used] eye exams can be performed in different ways. help of AI. The double slit experiment is not used directly. But only the method is used. Using this method eye examinations can be performed in different ways. it is possible to perform eye examinations in different ways using this method. Help of AI. Using AI.

If an eye examination, software is performed using the double slit experiment method, when we do an eye test, we give the objects, images, and letters in front of

us the nature of electrons as imaginary, not directly, but only imaginatively. at the same time, add the double slit experiment method to the eye examination device. Moreover the letters, objects and images in that device are using the double slit experiment method, and add that method to the images, objects and letters using the methods of that mechanical technology. Add double slit experiment method to the devices using mechanical methods and other technologies. The double slit experiment methods mentioned above can be used not only for devices but also for screens where eye testing is performed.

In devices made using the double slit experiment method or devices to which that method has been added, letters and pitches are placed in the disordering, so that if we can see them accurately, they are at the same level. We are not able to see the object clearly and precisely, it will turn into a wave form. Otherwise, eye tests can be conducted in different ways by giving letters, pictures and objects the imaginary nature of electrons and that too using only the double slit experiment method. By passing the latter or picture, latter or images and making changes in thickness according to the taste of the eye, when they come to the screen, they will all have a wave from. According to our eye vision, they all come to the same level. The reason is that the double slit experiment method is used only and is not used directly. The method can be tested in different ways by making transformations based on various technologies and methods. All the above are only one or two methods. Similarly, many methods can be used according to the situation and context and can be tested in different ways. that method is not used directly. Only the method is used. The method has been converted in various technologies. The reason is that it is not used directly here. Only the method is used.

With this method, if the objects we see are not visible to our eyes, we can see them in the form of waves, and if we observe them, we can bring them to a same level or to the same level. This method can be used to perform eye examinations in different ways. because this method can be transformed with the help of various software and technologies without making any changes to the method used here.

[the special feature of the double slit experiment is that in this theory, only the method is used without using the double slit experiment directly. The eye also works based on observation. Various types of tests can be performed based on the vision of the eye. when the eye is tested according to the vision that can be seen through the eye, if the double slit experiment method is added to it, and if that is also added in different ways, it can be converted in different ways. using the double slit experiment method, eye testing can be done in different ways, because only the experimental method is used, not directly].

The double slit experiment can be imaginatively added to devices and software. The objects observed during eye examinations can be imaginatively given the characteristics of particles tested in the double slit experiment, because here AI and other technologies are used based on the situation and context.

No device, software or mathematical calculation is mentioned here, because many different devices and software can be made using this method, and this method can be added to them. And mathematics can be used in different ways.

AI can be added in different ways and developed in different ways based on the situation and context we are measuring. The reason is that the double slit experiment is not used directly, but rather it is used in various ways.

Using the double slit experiment method, it is possible to create different software and devices for eye testing. This method can be added to eye testing devices, software and many other technologies. Help of AI. Instead of using it directly, depending on the design of the device and software, different testing methods can be performed using only the double slit experiment method, and similarly, depending on the design of the software, devices, and other technologies, different eye tests can be performed using the same method without making changes to the method. Using this method, it is possible to create different software and different devices. This method can be used on different devices and software's depending on the situation and context. This method can be used on different devices and software's.

By using AI this method automatically changes in various ways depending on the eye's condition. AI it can also be adjusted in different ways. if you adjust it in that way, double slit experiment this method will automatically change according to the eye's vision and you can it in different ways. since AI is used here, it automatically adjusts according to the eye's vision.

CONCLUSION

The theory is that without making changes to the double slit experiment method, it is possible to perform eye examinations in different ways by making modifications to technologies and software. It is also said that by adding this method to software and technologies, it is possible to perform eye examinations in different ways. the test can be done using various software and various devices without using the double slit experiment directly. It is possible to perform eye examinations in different ways by converting the method into software and equipment without making any changes to the method. This method will help discover new things related to the eye and conduct more experiment and observations.

AI also helps to discover different things. AI it helps to measure in different ways.

REFERENCE

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